

RESEARCH TRENDS ON BABINSA (VILLAGE SUPERVISORY NON-COMMISSIONED OFFICERS): SCIENTIFIC PERSPECTIVES, STUDY FOCUS, AND IMPLICATIONS

Hiras M. S. Turnip^{1)*}
Dislitbang TNI AD¹⁾
Email: hirasturnip@gmail.com*

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Abstract

This study analyses research trends on Babinsa (Bintara Pembina Desa/Village Management Senior NCO) based on fifty-two academic publications from 2013 to March 2025. The study aims to identify topic trends, dominant disciplines, temporal distribution, and research methodologies. Findings reveal a shift from a focus on security and public order to socio-economic empowerment, cross-sectoral collaboration, and technology utilization. Research is dominated by the Social-Political Sciences discipline and qualitative approaches. Gaps are found in regulatory aspects, long-term evaluation, and community-based perspectives. This study provides insights to support policymaking and enhance the effectiveness of Babinsa's role in society.

Keywords: Babinsa, research trends, territorial management, community empowerment, public policy.

A. INTRODUCTION

In accordance with the Territorial Doctrine of the Indonesian Army (TNI AD, 2022), territorial management is one of the main functions of the Indonesian Army in supporting national security stability and strengthening community welfare. The Technical Guidelines for Territorial Management (Pembinaan Teritorial) Implementation (TNI AD, 2021) explain that Village Management Senior NCO (Babinsa: Bintara Pembina Desa) are key elements that interact directly with the community at the village level. Babinsa has strategic tasks that include security, economic empowerment, crisis mitigation, and response to social dynamics, including the adaptation of digital technology in supporting the implementation of their duties (Susanto et al., 2023).

As noted by Latuheru et al. (2022), Babinsa acts as a link between national policies and the local context, strengthening state defense while improving community welfare. In the past decade, research on Babinsa has shown significant improvement, reflecting a shift in focus from security towards socio-economic empowerment, crisis management, and the use of technology in their tasks. This dynamic expands the scope of research and opens a space for discussion about the role of Babinsa in facing contemporary challenges, such as the response to COVID-19, national food security, and community digital literacy.

B. LITERATURE REVIEW

The Historical Context of Babinsa Studies

Academic studies on Babinsa began to gain attention in scientific publications in 2013. Initial research focused on the role of Babinsa in public security and order, which reflects

their primary duties as part of the country's defense system at the village level (Anggoro et al., 2024). These studies have discussed how Babinsa plays a role in maintaining social stability in village communities and preventing conflicts through security-based approaches. However, in the period 2013–2015, the number of publications on Babinsa was still limited, with only two studies identified.

A significant surge in publications began to be seen since 2016. In this period, research topics began to diversify, including community empowerment, disaster mitigation, and Babinsa's collaboration with local governments in development programs. The role of Babinsa began to expand in line with government policies that strengthened their involvement in supporting food security and socio-economic empowerment (TNI AD, 2021). In the next five years (2016–2020), the number of publications increased sharply with an average of research that became more diverse every year (Purnamasari et al., 2023).

The increase in academic attention continues in the 2021–2025 period. Research in this phase further highlights Babinsa's role in responding to contemporary issues such as the COVID-19 pandemic, the use of technology in community communication, and strengthening Babinsa's capacity as a social facilitator at the community level (Susanto et al., 2023). The peak of publication occurred in 2023, with nine studies published in one year (Haris, 2023).

Overall, the research focus on Babinsa has transformed from security to a more holistic strategic role, including socio-economic empowerment, task digitization, and cross-sector collaboration. These developments reflect the complexity of the challenges that Babinsa face in their tasks, which require a more in-depth study of the long-term impacts and effectiveness of related policies (Latuheru et al., 2022).

Topic Trends

Research on Babinsa shows a shift in focus from security to community empowerment and crisis management. Studies on community empowerment and capacity building in Babinsa began to dominate after 2020. However, the lack of study on regulations shows that the legal dimension related to Babinsa's role still receives less academic attention, although this aspect is important in determining the limitations of their authority in the civil realm (Sukriono et al., 2025).

Table-1 summarizes the distribution of research by main theme:

Table 1. Trends of research topics about Babinsa

TOPIC	FOCUS	NUMBER OF STUDIES	DOMINANT PERIOD
Public security and order.	Babinsa's role in public security and order, early detection, and conflict mitigation.	20	2013-2016, continued to be stable until 2020.
Community empowerment	Babinsa as a facilitator in economic, social, and food security development.	11	It has increased since 2016, stable until 2025.
Capacity and Performance Enhancement	Study on the competence, training, and effectiveness of Babinsa's performance.	8	Dominant after 2021.
Collaboration with civil institutions	Babinsa's synergy with local governments, police, and communities.	4	Stable since 2016, slightly increasing.
Disaster and crisis management	Babinsa's role in disaster and crisis management, including the COVID-19 pandemic.	4	Emerging after 2021, the trend is increasing.
Technology development	The use of digital technology and information systems in Babinsa's duties.	4	It was only after 2021 that the trend increased.

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Legal and Regulatory Aspects	A study of the regulation and legal limitations of the role of Babinsa in civil government.	1	Not specifically identified because there are still few.
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Source: results of data processing and analysis by the Author, 2025

Dominance of the Topic of Public Security and Order (Kamtibmas)

A total of twenty publications focuses on the role of Babinsa in maintaining public security and order (Kamtibmas). This research highlights Babinsa's contribution in early detection of potential conflicts, preventing radicalism, and maintaining social stability in the village. For example, Simanjuntak (2015) elaborated on how Babinsa plays a role in early detection for the prevention of terrorism in the region. This focus reflects Babinsa's fundamental task in territorial management, as stipulated in the Technical Guidelines for Territorial Management Implementation (TNI AD, 2021). This role remained the dominant topic until 2016 but began to be overshadowed by more diverse themes as the complexity of Babinsa's tasks increased.

Community Empowerment: A Stronger Focus

A total of eleven publications discusses the role of Babinsa in community empowerment, especially in the development of local economy, social, and food security (Napitupulu et al., 2022). This research shows that Babinsa not only plays a role as a security guard, but also as a facilitator of village community development (Rahmat et al., 2020). The increased focus on community empowerment also reflects the adaptation of Babinsa's role in dealing with contemporary issues, such as food security (Hariyanto et al., 2022).

Babinsa Capacity and Performance Enhancement

A total of eight studies highlights the importance of training, technology support, and internal policies in increasing the capacity of Babinsa (Helen & Elisa, 2024). This study reflects academic attention to the operational effectiveness of Babinsa in performing their duties. For example, Karyo (2017) and Putra (2022) who highlight the improvement of Babinsa's competence in territorial management tasks in the region.

Other Topics That Are Starting to Grow

Several other themes are starting to gain attention despite the limited number of publications:

- a. Cross-Sector Collaboration (4 publications): Babinsa acts as a liaison between local governments, police, and communities, especially in village development projects.
- b. Disaster and Crisis Management (4 publications): This study identifies Babinsa's contribution to disaster mitigation and post-disaster rehabilitation, including the COVID-19 pandemic.
- c. Technology Development (4 publications): This study discusses Babinsa's adaptation to technology, such as geospatial information systems for regional monitoring.
- d. Legal and Regulatory Aspects (1 publication): Studies on the regulation of Babinsa's role are still extremely limited, indicating the need for further exploration of the legal basis governing Babinsa's authority.

Temporal Distribution (Trend according to period)

The temporal distribution analysis of the research on Babinsa shows a significant upward trend in the last decade. Based on the available data, this study can be grouped into three main periods:

- a. Period 2013–2015: Beginning of an Academic Study on Babinsa. In this initial period, there were only two publications that focused on the role of Babinsa, with the main topic being public security and order (Kamtibmas). This research reflects the focus of Babinsa as part of the national defense system that is tasked with maintaining social stability at the

village level. However, academic studies in this period were still limited in the scope of topics and methodological approaches.

b. Period 2016–2020: Increased Interest and Topic Diversification. Research on Babinsa began to show a significant spike in this period, with a total of twenty publications. In addition to the topic of security, the study began to delve into the themes of community empowerment, disaster mitigation, and cross-sector collaboration. Government policies that strengthen Babinsa's involvement in village development programs have also encouraged the diversification of research topics in this phase. An example is Babinsa's role in supporting food security programs and their involvement in post-disaster rehabilitation.

c. Period 2021–2025: The Rise of the Babinsa Study. In this period, thirty publications were found, making it the phase with the largest number of studies. The surge in academic interest was influenced by contemporary issues, such as Babinsa's response to the COVID-19 pandemic, the digitization of their duties, and efforts to strengthen the socio-economic resilience of the community. The year 2023 recorded a peak of publication with nine published studies, reflecting the recognition of Babinsa's strategic role in addressing increasingly complex local and national challenges.

The following Diagram-2 shows how the various categories of research topics on Babinsa developed in three five-year periods: 2013-2015, 2016-2020, and 2021-2025.

Diagram-2. Temporal distribution of research on Babinsa based on five-year periods
Source: results of data processing and analysis by the Author, 2025

Meanwhile, trends of research topics in Babinsa studies over the years can be seen in the following Diagram-3:

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Diagram-3. Trends of research topics in Babinsa studies over the years (2013-2025)
Source: results of data processing and analysis by the Author, 2025

Research on Babinsa shows a shift in focus from public security and order to broader discussions, such as community empowerment, crisis management, and technology adaptation. This reflects the increasingly complex change in Babinsa's role to adapt to the needs of modern society.

However, there are important gaps regarding the regulatory and legal aspects that govern the role of Babinsa in their duties (Kidang et al., 2024). The lack of research in this area suggests the need for further exploration to provide a clear legal basis and support Babinsa's work more effectively.

Dominant Disciplines

Analysis of the disciplines in the study on Babinsa shows that this study is dominated by the Socio-Political field, which reflects the attention of academics to the role of Babinsa in social dynamics and local government. In addition, there are contributions from the fields of Public Administration, Management & Leadership, as well as several other disciplines such as Agriculture, Information Technology, and Law.

The distribution of disciplines in the study on Babinsa is as follows (see Diagram-4):

Diagram-4. The proportion of disciplines in research on Babinsa
Source: results of data processing and analysis by the Author, 2025

a. **Dominance of Socio-Political Studies** (29 publications). The Socio-Political Field dominates research on Babinsa with twenty-nine publications. The main factors that cause this dominance include:

1) The role of Babinsa in maintaining socio-political stability. Babinsa has the main task of territorial management which is closely related to political stability and security at the village level. Their interaction with local governments, civil society, and other strategic groups is an important aspect that attracts the attention of academics in the field of socio-political sciences.

2) The context of national policy and security sector reform. In recent years, there have been policy changes that have expanded the role of Babinsa, not only in the field of defense, but also in village development, economic empowerment, and disaster mitigation. This change prompted more research in the socio-political field that highlighted how the policy affected the role and effectiveness of Babinsa.

3) Related to national and global strategic issues. The study of Babinsa in the socio-political field is also influenced by national and global issues, such as radicalism, social conflicts, elections, and the response to the pandemic. In many cases, Babinsa are often at the forefront of maintaining social stability at the local level, so their role continues to be the object of study from a political and security perspective.

b. **Public Administration and Leadership Management** (5 publications each). The fields of Public Administration and Management & Leadership have five publications each, with a primary focus on the effectiveness of Babinsa's work programs as well as their leadership strategies in the field. Some of the factors that influence the emergence of studies in this discipline include:

1) Babinsa as an actor in the village government bureaucracy. Although Babinsa come from military institutions, in practice they often function as an extension of the government in various village development programs. This attracted the attention of academics in the field of public administration to research how Babinsa collaborated with village officials in the implementation of policies (Banjar et al., 2023).

2) Babinsa's leadership at the local level. In the context of management and leadership, Babinsa often function as informal leaders in their communities. Studies in this area discuss how Babinsa's leadership style influences community participation in development programs, as well as how they manage relationships with other local actors.

c. **Agriculture** (4 publications): Babinsa as a Supporter of Food Security. The study of Babinsa in agriculture is quite significant with four publications, which are influenced by their role in supporting national food security programs. The main factors that cause this include:

1) The TNI AD program in food security. In recent years, the Indonesian Army has actively supported food security programs through farmer assistance by Babinsa. Their involvement in agricultural counselling, distribution of seed aid, and the coaching of farmer groups has become an interesting topic in academic studies.

2) Cross-sectoral cooperation in agricultural development. Many studies highlight the collaboration between Babinsa and the Ministry of Agriculture and the regional agriculture office in optimizing food production at the village level. This shows that Babinsa not only plays a role in security, but also in the economic aspects of rural communities.

d. **Information Technology** (4 publications): Digital Adaptation in Babinsa's Task. Babinsa's role in the use of information technology began to attract the attention of academics, with four publications discussing how they use technology in performing their duties. Some of the factors that prompted this study include:

1) Digital transformation in village government. The government has encouraged digitalization in various aspects of village administration, including in the monitoring and communication system. Babinsa, as an important actor in the village community, has also adapted to these changes, for example by using community complaint applications, GIS-based mapping of areas, and online communication with local governments.

2) The role of technology in the effectiveness of Babinsa's work. Studies in the field of information technology discuss how the use of technology can improve the efficiency of Babinsa's work, for example in collecting citizen data, reporting socio-political conditions, and coordinating with other agencies.

e. **Law** (3 publications): Lack of Babinsa Regulation Studies. The legal discipline only has three publications, which shows that the regulatory aspects related to the role of Babinsa still lack academic attention. Some of the factors that affect the lack of studies in this field are:

1) Lack of research on the limitations of Babinsa's authority. Babinsa's role is often at the intersection of military and civilian duties. However, there are still few studies that specifically discuss the limitations of Babinsa's authority in national law, especially related to interventions in civil policy, law enforcement, and involvement in local government programs.

2) The high sensitivity of military-related legal issues. Some of the legal aspects related to Babinsa's role, such as their involvement in politics or constitutional law, are sensitive topics and are often avoided in academic research.

Overall, the dominance of Socio-Political disciplines shows that research on Babinsa is still more often studied in the context of policy and social stability than in other technical aspects. However, the increasing number of studies in the fields of Public Administration, Management, Agriculture, and Information Technology shows that there is a diversification of topics that lead to a broader understanding of the role of Babinsa in various sectors of people's lives.

The lack of studies in the field of Law is one of the research gaps that need to be considered, considering that the regulatory aspect is particularly important in determining the limitations of Babinsa's authority in performing their duties. In addition, the field of Information Technology also has the potential to be further developed, especially in the context of digitizing Babinsa's tasks.

Research Methodology

The analysis of the research methodology used in the study on Babinsa showed the dominance of the qualitative approach, with a much higher number of publications than the quantitative or mixed method. Of the fifty-two publications analysed, forty-four used a qualitative approach, seven used a quantitative approach, and one used a mixed approach.

The distribution of research methodologies in the study of Babinsa is as follows (see Diagram-5):

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Diagram-5. Distribution of research methodology on Babinsa
Source: results of data processing and analysis by the Author, 2025

While the following Diagram-6 shows how the research methodology (qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods) used in a variety of disciplines:

Diagram-6. Distribution of research methodologies across disciplines
Source: results of data processing and analysis by the Author, 2025

Dominance of Qualitative Approaches

Qualitative methods dominate almost all disciplines, especially in the fields of Socio-Politics and Public Administration (Tureta et al., 2021). This shows that the study of Babinsa explores social phenomena more through interviews, observations, and policy analysis. This approach dominates research on Babinsa, due to several key factors:

- a. Babinsa as a subject with a complex social context. Babinsa's role in territorial management involves close social interaction with the community, local governments, and other actors. Qualitative studies allow for an in-depth exploration of the dynamics of these relationships, which are difficult to measure with quantitative methods.
- b. Focus on policy analysis and case studies. Many studies on Babinsa discuss government policies, program implementation strategies, and the social impact of Babinsa interventions. Qualitative methods are more suitable for use in policy studies because they provide deeper insights into the role of Babinsa in various socio-political contexts.
- c. The main data is sourced from interviews and observations. Studies on Babinsa generally use in-depth interviews with Babinsa itself, local government officials, and the communities they foster. In addition, field observations are often used to understand how Babinsa perform their duties in real conditions.

Quantitative Methods

Quantitative methods are still limited, used only in a few studies in the fields of Management & Leadership and Agriculture. Although less than the qualitative method, there are seven studies that use a quantitative approach, for example Astuti et al. (2021) which try to measure farmers' perceptions of the role of Babinsa in Upsus Pajale (Special efforts for rice, corn, and soybean production). Some of the factors that cause the limited quantitative research in the Babinsa study are:

- a. The difficulty of obtaining statistical data related to Babinsa. Most of Babinsa's assignments are qualitative and field experience-based, making them difficult to quantify in the form of numbers or statistical models. Data on the effectiveness of Babinsa's programs are often not systematically documented in the form of statistically analysable numbers.
- b. Quantitative research tends to focus on surveys or secondary data analysis. Existing quantitative studies usually use survey methods to the community or village officials to measure the impact of the presence of Babinsa in an area. Some studies also use secondary data such as government reports or official Indonesian Army (TNI AD) publications to conduct simple statistical analysis.

Mixed Methods

Mixed Methods are hardly used, indicating that research on Babinsa rarely combines qualitative and quantitative data to produce a more comprehensive analysis. Only one publication used a mixed approach, namely research by Arifin (2022) which highlights the role of Babinsa in flood disaster management and its implications for the resilience of its region. The lack of use of mixed methods in the study of Babinsa can be caused by:

- a. High complexity in mixed research design. Mixed methods research requires the collection and analysis of two types of data (qualitative and quantitative) simultaneously, which often require greater resources and longer time.
- b. Babinsa's research often focuses on exploratory aspects rather than predictive. Since most of the research on Babinsa is still in the exploration stage of social phenomena, a qualitative approach takes precedence over an approach that incorporates quantitative methods to measure the relationship between variables.

The dominance of qualitative methods in the study of Babinsa shows that research focuses more on narratives, insights, and understanding of social phenomena than quantitative measurements based on statistical data. While this approach provides a rich understanding of Babinsa's role, there are several implications to be noted:

- a. Lack of numbers-based data that can be used for policy evaluation. Qualitative studies are often difficult to use as a basis for evidence-based policymaking. Therefore, more quantitative research is needed that objectively measures the impact of Babinsa's intervention.
- b. Opportunities for the development of quantitative and mixed methods. To complement the insights provided by qualitative studies, further research can develop quantitative models, such as analysis of the socio-economic impact of the Babinsa program, the effectiveness of Babinsa's work based on specific indicators, or the use of big data in monitoring Babinsa's activities in various regions.
- c. Opportunities for the use of technology in data collection. With the development of information technology, research on Babinsa can use social media analysis, automated text processing, or spatial data analysis to complement existing qualitative approaches.

Overall, research on Babinsa is still heavily dominated by qualitative methods, reflecting a primary focus on social exploration, policy, and community interaction. Meanwhile, quantitative research is still limited, and mixed approaches are hardly used. In the future, more research is needed with a quantitative approach and mixed methods to provide broader

and data-driven insights on the effectiveness of Babinsa's role in various aspects of community development.

C. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses a literature analysis method with a simple bibliometric approach to see how the study of Babinsa develops from year to year (Kangana et al., 2024). The bibliometric method is a quantitative technique used to analyse the pattern of scientific publications based on metadata, such as the number of research, temporal distribution, topic categories, disciplines, and research methodologies used (Donthu et al., 2021). This approach is often used in academic studies to identify research trends, author networks, and concept evolution in a field of study (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017). The bibliometric method has several advantages, namely providing a systematic overview of research trends, allowing the detection of publication patterns, and helping to identify research gaps (Jing et al., 2024). However, this method also has limitations, including only focusing on publication metadata so that it does not dig into the content of the research in depth. In addition, the results of the analysis are highly dependent on the availability of digital data, so studies that are not documented online may not be accessible by this method.

In this study, the quality of literature as a scientific publication which is usually measured by indexation in reputable databases is also excluded, considering that the topic of Babinsa is specific and very "local" in Indonesia. This has led to less literature available compared to topics of universal relevance, such as the military in general or defense studies. Therefore, the focus of the research is directed at the digital literature available up to the analysis period to ensure relevance to the objectives of this study.

Data obtained from academic article search engines Google Scholar with the keyword "Babinsa", or "Village Guidance Non-Commissioned Officers", or "Village Supervisory Non-Commissioned Officers" in the title. The search results cover the period 2013 – March 2025, with further filtering through other academic databases such as Sinta (<https://sinta.kemdikbud.go.id/>), Garuda (<https://garuda.kemdikbud.go.id/>), and publisher websites. The data collection process involves the following steps:

1. Literature Validation: Literature that meets academic criteria is verified based on titles, abstracts, and content, with exceptions for non-academic articles, news reports, as well as publications that are not relevant to Babinsa's focus.
2. Elimination of Duplication: Articles that are republished on different platforms or written in different languages are removed to ensure there is no duplicate data.
3. Thematic Screening: The literature is classified based on relevance to key focuses, such as security, community empowerment, and technological adaptation.

Only literature available in digital format until 19 March 2025 was analysed. Military internal reports or scientific papers that are not widely published are excluded, so the results of the analysis may have limited representation on some specific themes. In addition, literature that only mentions Babinsa at a glance without being the main focus was also not included in the analysis.

The following Diagram-1 illustrates the flow of literature selection and screening:

Diagram-1. Literature Selection and Screening Flow
Source: Created by Author, 2025

The analysis was conducted by grouping research based on the main theme (topic category), temporal distribution, discipline, and methodology used. For example, research by Rahmat et al. (2020) is categorized under the topic 'Community Empowerment' because it discusses the role of Babinsa in improving village welfare. Meanwhile, the study by Arifin (2022) is included in the category of 'Disaster Management' because it analyses Babinsa's contribution to natural disaster mitigation in flood-prone areas. The data is then visualized in the form of tables and diagrams or graphs to illustrate the development pattern of research on Babinsa in various aspects.

In this study, the bibliometric method was conducted manually without using special software such as VOSviewer or Bibliometrix. This is due to the amount of literature that is still on a scale that can be managed directly (52 articles). If the volume of literature is larger (e.g., hundreds or thousands of publications), the use of software can help in the automation of inter-research relationship analysis and more complex visualizations.

D. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Practical Implications

From the analysis of the research, there are several important implications that can be applied to policies and practices in the field:

- a. **Capacity Building of Babinsa as an Agent of Socio-Economic Transformation.** Studies show that the scope of Babinsa's duties has extended beyond security to areas of socio-economic empowerment. Additional training in crisis management, entrepreneurship, digital literacy, and information technology can increase Babinsa's effectiveness in supporting the development of an independent community. This effort is also relevant to modern needs in the digital era.
- b. **Strengthening Multi-Sector Collaboration.** The research highlights the need for synergy between Babinsa, local governments, the private sector, and civil society. Closer collaboration can increase the success of programs such as food security, disaster mitigation, and community empowerment. As a cross-sector liaison, Babinsa needs communication and coordination training to optimize this role.
- c. **Utilization of Technology in Babinsa Operations.** Several studies have underlined the role of technology in supporting Babinsa's work, such as geospatial information systems (GIS), community complaint reporting applications, and social media to build communication with citizens. For example, Syam et al. (2023) who researched Babinsa's digital literacy ability to increase people's readiness to face natural disasters. The TNI AD can adopt a more

systematic digitalization strategy to improve the efficiency and accuracy of Babinsa's tasks in the field.

d. **More Comprehensive Policy Evaluation.** The research highlights the gaps in the regulations that govern the boundaries of Babinsa's authority, especially in cross-sectoral tasks. Evidence-based policies are needed to formulate clear guidelines and prevent overlapping roles of Babinsa with other civil servants, thereby creating better governance.

Research Gaps

Although research on Babinsa has evolved, there are still some significant shortcomings, which create opportunities for further study:

a. **Lack of Quantitative Studies.** Most studies use a descriptive qualitative approach. A more measurable quantitative study is needed to evaluate the impact of the Babinsa program on community welfare, the effectiveness of village development, and socio-economic stability in the target area.

b. **Lack of Long-Term Research.** Many studies have focused only on short-term interventions, such as post-disaster emergency response. Longitudinal research is needed to evaluate the effectiveness of Babinsa in dealing with social changes and long-term dynamics in society.

c. **Limited Community Perspective.** Research tends to focus on institutional perspectives. A study that explores the community's views on Babinsa's performance can provide new insights into how their contribution is perceived by residents.

d. **Lack of Regulatory and Legal Studies.** A large gap is found in the legal aspects that regulate the limitations of Babinsa's authority in civil and military duties. Research that explores this legal umbrella is needed to strengthen the legitimacy and effectiveness of Babinsa's role in various regions.

e. **The Use of Technology for Babinsa Research.** Research on Babinsa can draw on the analysis big data, social media, and GIS to identify patterns of activity and the impact of their interventions in different regions. This data-driven approach will complement the traditional methods that have been used.

f. **Comparative Studies Between Regions.** Most of Babinsa's studies are still locally based. Comparative research that compares the role of Babinsa in regions with different socio-economic characteristics can provide strategic insights for approaches tailored to local needs.

E. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of research trends on Babinsa in the period 2013 to March 2025, there are a number of main findings that can be summarized:

The Evolution of Research Focus. Research on Babinsa shows a significant increase in the past decade. The initial study focused a lot on the aspect of public security and order (Kamtibmas) which is the traditional role of Babinsa. However, over time, the focus of research shifted towards community empowerment, crisis mitigation, and technology adaptation. This shift reflects the expansion of Babinsa's role as an actor that supports village development and socio-economic resilience.

Dominance of Socio-Political Science Disciplines and Qualitative Methodology. Socio-Political Disciplines dominate research on Babinsa, showing great concern for their role in social stability and public policy. On the other hand, the dominance of qualitative methods shows the focus of exploration of social interaction and policy. Lack of quantitative and mixed methods creates opportunities for more measurable data-driven research.

Increasing the Role of Babinsa in the Modern Era. Research in the 2021–2025 period further highlights Babinsa's adaptation to modern challenges, such as the response to the

COVID-19 pandemic, strengthening food security, and the use of technology. This shows the academic recognition of the importance of Babinsa in dealing with contemporary issues.

4. **Gaps in Academic Studies.** Several significant research gaps were found, including the lack of quantitative studies that measured the impact of the role of Babinsa, the lack of long-term research, and the lack of studies that explored regulations and community perspectives. This is a challenge as well as an opportunity for future research.

Recommendations

To encourage the development of research and the effectiveness of Babinsa's role, it is recommended:

Improving quantitative studies and mixed methods to provide empirical evidence on the impact of Babinsa interventions. Conduct long-term research to evaluate the Babinsa program more comprehensively. Expanding the research focus on Babinsa's role in the digital and technology realm. Exploring the community's perspective regarding Babinsa's performance to enrich understanding of the relevance of their role.

Appendix: Literature Data.

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1IHEHwnmMTFRZMRgzO3OqzLfH0VhgZ390/view?usp=sharing>

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